

Appendix B

Existing Climatology Data

LIST OF EXHIBITS

<u>EXHIBIT TITLE</u>	<u>EXHIBIT NUMBER</u>
HISPANIOLA – WEATHER STATIONS SPATIAL COVERAGE	B-1
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE ANNUAL RAINFALL DEPTH	B-2
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE JANUARY RAINFALL DEPTH	B-3
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE FEBRUARY RAINFALL DEPTH	B-4
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE MARCH RAINFALL DEPTH	B-5
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE APRIL RAINFALL DEPTH	B-6
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE MAY RAINFALL DEPTH	B-7
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE JUNE RAINFALL DEPTH	B-8
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE JULY RAINFALL DEPTH	B-9
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE AUGUST RAINFALL DEPTH	B-10
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE SEPTEMBER RAINFALL DEPTH	B-11
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE OCTOBER RAINFALL DEPTH	B-12
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE NOVEMBER RAINFALL DEPTH	B-13
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE DECEMBER RAINFALL DEPTH	B-14
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE ANNUAL POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-15
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE JANUARY POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-16
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE FEBRUARY POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-17
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE MARCH POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-18
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE APRIL POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-19
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE MAY POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-20
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE JUNE POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-21
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE JULY POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-22
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE AUGUST POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-23
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE SEPTEMBER POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-24
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE OCTOBER POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-25

HAITI – GIS-Based Hydropower Potential Mapping

HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE NOVEMBER POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-26
HISPANIOLA – AVERAGE DECEMBER POTENTIAL EVAPO-TRANSPIRATION DEPTH	B-27

LEGEND

	Weather Station		DOMINICAN REPUBLIC CITIES		GEO-POLITICAL BOUNDARIES
	HAITI CITIES		Capital Departamento		Departements
	Chef Lieu		Capital		Departamentos
	Capital				

HISPANIOLA WEATHER STATIONS SPATIAL COVERAGE

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE JANUARY RAINFALL DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE FEBRUARY RAINFALL DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE MARCH RAINFALL DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE APRIL RAINFALL DEPTH

LEGEND

MAY RAINFALL DEPTH (mm)

HAITI CITIES

- ★ Chef Lieu
- ★ Capital

DOMINICAN REPUBLIC CITIES

- ★ Capital Departamento
- ★ Capital

GEO-POLITICAL BOUNDARIES

- Departements
- Departamentos

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE MAY RAINFALL DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE AUGUST RAINFALL DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE SEPTEMBER RAINFALL DEPTH

LEGEND

OCTOBER RAINFALL DEPTH (mm)

HAITI CITIES

- ★ Chef Lieu
- ★ Capital

DOMINICAN REPUBLIC CITIES

- ★ Capital Departamento
- ★ Capital

GEO-POLITICAL BOUNDARIES

- Departements
- Departamentos

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE OCTOBER RAINFALL DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE NOVEMBER RAINFALL DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE DECEMBER RAINFALL DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE ANNUAL POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE JANUARY POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE FEBRUARY POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE MARCH POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE APRIL POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE MAY POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE JUNE POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE JULY POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE AUGUST POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

LEGEND

OCTOBER PET DEPTH (mm)

HAITI CITIES

- ★ Chef Lieu
- ★ Capital

DOMINICAN REPUBLIC CITIES

- ★ Capital Departamento
- ★ Capital

GEO-POLITICAL BOUNDARIES

- Departements
- Departamentos

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE OCTOBER POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE NOVEMBER POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

HISPANIOLA AVERAGE DECEMBER POTENTIAL EVAPORATION DEPTH

